

Identification of odour-important norisoprenoids in *Arbutus pavarii* honey

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Abstract

Arbutus pavarii honey is a rare and expensive honey derived from the floral nectar of the wild strawberry tree *Arbutus pavarii* pamp. This study focused on the identification and characterisation of norisoprenoids responsible for its unique savoury, saffron-like aroma. Volatile components (from honey samples collected over three years 2015, 2016, 2017) were isolated by continuous liquid-liquid extraction (cLLE) combined with solvent-assisted flavour evaporation (SAFE) and the potent odorants determined by GC-olfactometry, aroma extract dilution analysis (AEDA) and GC-MS. Seventeen norisoprenoids and two additional isophorone derivatives were detected, 14 of which were positively identified and their concentrations determined by stable isotope dilution analysis (SIDA)-HS-SPME-GC-(TOF)MS. Results indicated that lanierone (**1**) was the most important odorant, while α -isophorone (**4**) was the most abundant norisoprenoid in *Arbutus pavarii* honey.

Keywords: honey, *Arbutus pavarii*, odorants, norisoprenoids, lanierone

Introduction

Monofloral honeys often possess unique volatile fingerprints that distinguish them from other honeys, especially multifloral types. A type of monofloral honey produced in Libya, known locally as honnoon or bitter honey, is derived from the flower nectar of the wild strawberry or shmary tree (*Arbutus pavarii* pamp., family Ericaceae) [1]. This tree is endemic to Libya but is scarce and vulnerable to potential extinction [2], which in turn causes *A. pavarii* honey to be quite rare and expensive. This honey is characterised by its bitter taste and its unique savoury saffron-like aroma. Although various qualitative criteria have been established for *A. pavarii* honey, there are no published reports regarding its characteristic aroma constituents. Therefore, the purpose of this study was to identify and characterise the odorants responsible for the savoury aroma in *A. pavarii* honey.

Experimental

Aroma profiling of one representative sample of *A. pavarii* honey (sample 2017) was carried out by descriptive sensory aroma analysis according to the method described by Zhou et al. (2002) [3] using a 9-member trained panel (4 female and 5 male, university students and staff, age 20 to 58 years).

The volatile components of *A. pavarii* honey samples were isolated by continuous liquid-liquid extraction (cLLE) combined with solvent-assisted flavour evaporation (SAFE).

GC-O analysis of the concentrated cLLE/SAFE extracts and serial dilutions of each extract was performed using a 6890N GC (Agilent Technologies Inc., Santa Clara, CA) equipped with a flame ionization detector (FID), a sniff port (DATU Technology Transfer, Geneva, NY) and a cool on-column injector (+3 °C oven tracking mode). Separations were performed on either RTX®- Stabilwax or RTX®-5 GC column (30 m x 0.25 mm i.d. x 0.25 μ m film thickness; Restek, Bellefonte, PA).

A GC-MS-O system consisted of an olfactory detector (ODP2, Gerstel, Germany) and a 6890 GC/5973N mass selective detector (Agilent Technologies, Inc). cLLE/SAFE extracts were injected (2 μ L) by cold splitless injection mode using a CIS4 inlet (Gerstel). Separations were performed on either a Stabilwax-DA® or Rxi-5ms-sil (30 m x 0.25 mm i.d. x 0.25 μ m df; Restek, Bellefonte, PA) capillary column. Column effluent was split between the MS detector and olfactory detection port. The mass spectra were recorded in full scan mode (35-300 amu, scan rate 5.27 scans/s, interface temperature 250°C, and ionization energy 70 eV.).

Quantitation of selected odorants was performed by SIDA combined with HS-SPME, and GC-(TOF)MS. Samples (0.1 to 1 g) in 22-mL vials were spiked with appropriate levels of labelled internal standards (IS) before analysis using a CombiPal autosampler (Leap Technologies, Inc., Fort Lauderdale, FL) connected to a 7890A GC (Agilent Technologies, Inc.) time-of-flight mass spectrometer [(TOF)MS; Pegasus 4D; LECO®, St. Joseph, MI]. Sample vial was pre-incubated at 60 °C for 10 min at an agitator speed of 250 rpm. A 2 cm, 50/30 μ m DVB/CAR/PDMS SPME fibre (Supelco Co., Bellefonte, PA, USA) was then exposed to the headspace of the sample vial for 30 minutes at the same temperature. The SPME fibre was inserted into the GC injector for desorption, hot splitless mode, at 260 °C with 4 min. valve delay, then kept in the inlet for an addition 20 min for post injection fibre conditioning. Analysis was carried out using a Stabilwax® GC column (30 m x 0.25 mm

id \times 0.25 μ m film thickness; Restek). Mass spectra were acquired at m/z range of 35 to 300 amu; electron multiplier voltage, Autotune + 200 V; and a scan rate of 50 scans/s. Peak areas for selected ions of target analytes/IS were determined using Leco Chroma TOF software (version 3.34).

Odour-activity values (OAVs) for potent odorants were calculated by dividing their concentrations by their odour detection thresholds (ODTs) in water.

Results and discussion

To characterise the aroma profile of *A. pavarii* honey, the overall aroma and 4 defined aroma attributes of *A. pavarii* honey were evaluated; namely, saffron-like, phenolic, caramellic and raisin-like aroma. Results indicated that savoury, saffron-like aroma was the predominant aroma attribute of this honey (Figure 1).

Figure 1: Sensory descriptive aroma profile of *Arbutus pavarii* honey (sample 2017).

Figure 2: Structures of selected norisoprenoids identified in *A. pavarii* honey (Compound numbers correspond to those in Table 1).

Sixty-nine aroma-active compounds were detected by GC-O and GC-MS. AEDA results indicated that the predominant odorants were norisoprenoids. A total 16 were norisoprenoids were detected along with two trimethylphenols which are known to be derived from isophorone. Twelve of the norisoprenoids and the two trimethylphenols (**5** and **6**) were positively identified and their concentrations and OAVs in *A. pavarii* honey determined (Figure 2, Table 1). Both FD factors and OAVs ranked lanierone (**1**) as the most potent odourant among all other volatile constituents of *A. pavarii* honey, followed by 2-hydroxyisophorone (**2**) (indicated only by its high FD factor since its OAV could not be calculated due to lack of an ODT). In addition, the results showed that α -isophorone was the most abundant volatile component of this honey. Some of the identified norisoprenoids, such as lanierone (**1**), 2-hydroxyisophorone (**2**), 4-hydroxyisophorone, 4-oxoisophorone, levodione and the two trimethylphenols (**5** and **6**) may exist either naturally in *A. pavarii* honey or could possibly be generated from α -isophorone (**4**) through chemical reactions [4] or through microbial conversions [5].

Table 1: FD Factors and OAVs of selected norisoprenoids in *A. pavarii* honey.

No.	Compound	FD ^a			OAV ^b		
		2015	2016	2017	2015	2016	2017
1	2-hydroxy-4,4,6-trimethylcyclohexa-2,5-dienone (lanierone)	59049 (19683)	59049 (19683)	59049 (19683)	6320	5680	6700
2	2-hydroxy-3,5,5-trimethylcyclohexa-2-enone (2-hydroxyisophorone)	2187 (2187)	2187 (2187)	2187 (2187)	NA	NA	NA
3	1-(2,6,6-trimethyl-1,3-cyclohexadien-1-yl)-2-buten-1-one (β -damascenone)	729 (2187)	729 (2187)	2187 (2187)	187	238	118
4	3,5,5-trimethylcyclohexa-2-enone (α -isophorone)	81 (729)	81 (729)	243 (729)	35	29	27
5	3,4,5-trimethylphenol	729 (81)	729 (81)	729 (243)	NA	NA	NA
6	2,3,5-trimethylphenol	729 (ND)	729 (ND)	729 (ND)	NA	NA	NA
7	2,6,6-trimethylcyclohexa-1,3-dienecarbaldehyde (safranal)	243 (27)	729 (27)	729 (27)	0.9	1.6	0.9

^a Average of three replications; FD values on Rtx-Wax (FD values on Rtx-5 column are given in parenthesis);

^b Odour-activity values (OAV) calculated by dividing average concentration by the odour detection threshold (ODT); ND: not detected; NA: not available due to lack of ODT values in literature.

Conclusion

This research represents the first to comprehensively characterise norisoprenoids in *A. pavarii* honey. GC analysis results of this study showed that norisoprenoids are the main attributors of *A. pavarii* honey aroma with lanierone being the most important odorant and α -isophorone the most abundant odorant among other odour-active constituents of this honey. Twelve norisoprenoids were positively identified in this study, some of them, such as, 2-hydroxy-4,4,6-trimethylcyclohexa-2,5-dienone (lanierone), 3,5,5-trimethyl-4-methylene-2-cyclohexene-1-one (4-methylene isophorone), have not been reported earlier in any other type of honey.

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